

Objective Evaluation of Imager Performance

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Abstract— We describe a method by which the evaluation and characterization of the performance of an imager can be done objectively and scientifically, that is, without routine operator interpretation. Although this method is demonstrated herein for passive long-wave infrared imagers (thermal infrared cameras) used by firefighters, it is applicable to any imaging system.

Keywords- human perception; image quality indicators; imager performance; test and evaluation

I. INTRODUCTION

Imaging systems are typically, if not always, characterized with a human in the loop to observe images and subsequently assess image quality. Although imagers have historically been evaluated this way because it is logical (the purpose of the imager is to present to the human an image of sufficient quality to perform a function), it is very subjective because of the variability of perception among a set of observers and the variability over time for a given observer. From a measurement science perspective, one important ability that is needed is a quantitative way of measuring the impact of human perception on image-based task performance and then to use that information to develop operator-independent imager evaluation methods.

The US Army's Night Vision and Electronic Sensors Directorate (NVESD, formerly the Night Vision Lab) has done significant work that is related to our goal. They have developed a multi-parameter (exceeding 100 parameters) model called NVTherm [1] that is used to compute imager performance for a given task. These parameters include detector physics, array electronics, physical optics, atmospheric propagation, etc., and are used to predict how well a particular imager will perform. This model is important to the Army to facilitate the development and deployment of an appropriate imager. Of the many parameters in the model, four are attributed to the human observer. To get values for these four parameters, NVESD uses a pre-determined number of test subjects to view a set of images. The test subjects attempt to perform perception tasks as the values of various image quality

indicators (IQIs) are varied. These IQIs can include, for example, spatial resolution, dynamic range, and noise floor.

We have developed a related method, but one more directed to characterization rather than prediction of imager performance. Consequently, we need only be concerned with the imager's IQIs (objective performance metrics) and how their variation affects task performance. Our method to characterize imager performance requires three steps. The first step is to identify unique IQIs that relate to the operational or field performance requirements (see Section II A) of the users for which the imager was designed. These IQIs must also be objectively, scientifically, reproducibly, repeatably, and accurately measureable in a laboratory. The performance evaluation of thermal imagers used by the fire service is given as a use case example in the following text. The second step is the development of scientific test and evaluation (T&E) methods to assess the imager, including test objects, scenes, and scenarios. These T&E methods must be validated to ensure the imagers are exercised over the full range of their operating parameters (see Section II B). The third step is the development of a scientifically-rigorous, statistically-valid one-time test of the effect of human perception on task performance for varying values of the IQIs (see Section II C). With these steps completed, we can develop a single formula that simultaneously relates the probability of successful task performance to all of the IQIs (see Section III). This method confers a few distinct advantages over existing methods:

1. Human-in-the-loop testing is eliminated except for the initial testing, thus greatly reducing subjectivity and variability in imager performance assessment.
2. The time and cost of all subsequent testing are reduced because testing can be done automatically in a lab.
3. The single formula to assess the performance of an imager allows the values of individual IQIs to wax and wane while providing the imager an avenue to meet the overall requirement. This flexibility maximizes procurement options and promotes technology development.
4. This methodology can be applied to any imager technology: static (still), dynamic (motion, video),

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monochromatic, color, multi- or hyper-spectral, and from x ray to radio frequency.

5. This methodology, with appropriate selection of IQIs, can be adapted for machine vision.

II. MEASUREMENT METHOD

As previously mentioned, we will use firefighter thermal imaging cameras (TICs) to demonstrate application of our method for characterizing imager performance. The advantage of using TICs for this demonstration work is that the design and wavelengths used by TICs result in images that range from nearly indecipherable to very intelligible and highly resolved. We use images from a high-quality scientific grade thermal imager as our reference images. Details of the correlation between the IQIs and the test methods described in Sections II A and II B can be found in Amon and Lock [2].

A. Identification of Image Quality Indicators

Fire service TICs are long-wave infrared (LWIR) imagers that operate in the 8 μm to 14 μm wavelength range. This relatively transmissive range is bounded by interference from water vapor and carbon dioxide on either side, both of which are commonly found in fire environments. Firefighters may rely on a TIC to aid their navigation through a burning structure; therefore most imagers employ a wide field of view (FOV) in the range of 40° to 60°. Most TICs feature fully automated gain, focus, and iris settings, generally offering few manual controls other than a large on/off button that can easily be accessed by a fire fighter wearing heavy gloves. The IQIs that are unique, independent, and can be used to assess operational requirements are:

1) Contrast (C) - a measure of the differences in intensity of the pixels in an image. In this work, $C = 0$ indicates an image in which all the pixels have the same intensity value, and $C = 1$ means that half of the pixels have zero intensity and half the pixels have the maximum possible intensity.

2) Brightness (B) - a measure of the average pixel intensity of an image. Here, $B = 0$ indicates a completely black image and $B = 1$ indicates a completely white image.

3) Spatial Resolution (R) - a measure of the amount of detail available in an image. In this work, $R = 0$ indicates that none of the pixels in an image are distinct. The maximum R value depends on the imager's detector design but is related to a length scale and the number of distinctly perceived pixels in the image.

4) Noise (N) - a measure of the imperfections in an image. For this work, noise includes contributions from electronic signal processing, optical aberrations, and design and material limitations. $N = 0$ indicates that there is no image degradation due to any TIC component. There is no theoretical ceiling on N .

B. Development of T&E Methods, Including Test Objects

A brief description of the laboratory test methods used to assess the TIC performance is presented in the following three subsections, see [2] for more detail.

i. Nonuniformity (NU) is a measure of the TIC's response to a uniform thermal target [3, 4]. There are many ways that the TIC response may be nonuniform [5]: gradients in pixel intensity across the image, various pattern aberrations, broadband noise, blemishes, blotches, and combinations of all these. Recognizing that many of these manifestations of NU are difficult to characterize, a measurement of broadband noise was chosen to represent NU . For our purposes, we define NU as:

$$NU = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

where σ and μ are the standard deviation and mean of pixel intensities within a user-defined area of the image. Three tests for each TIC are conducted at each of five target temperatures: 1 °C, 30 °C, 100 °C, 160 °C, and 260 °C, which span the temperature range of interest to the fire service [6]. This test results in a single, averaged value for NU . Well-characterized extended-area blackbodies are used as targets. The TIC under test is positioned such that the image of the blackbody surface completely fills the field of view and the TIC optical axis is normal to the plane of the blackbody surface. An image of the TIC's display for each of these tests is captured with a high-resolution digital visible camera for which σ and μ are calculated using image processing techniques.

ii. Spatial Resolution (R) is measured by viewing an image on the TIC's display with a high-resolution digital visible camera while the TIC views a thermal target comprising two sets of converging lines, as shown in Figure 1. The digital visible images are numerically processed to determine the spatial frequency at which the lines in the target are no longer differentiable. This test is performed three times for each TIC and the results are averaged to determine R . The target is a portion of the target used by the ISO Spatial Resolution Standard, ISO 12233 [7]. The target foreground and background are coated with well-characterized black paint having an emissivity of 0.94 ± 0.05 (as claimed by the paint manufacturer). The TIC under test is placed 1 m from the target, with optical axis normal to the plane of the target, and oriented to focus on the center of the target.

Figure 1: Spatial resolution thermal target. The foreground (black markings) is held at a constant temperature of 3 °C above ambient. The target size is 61 cm measured along the centerline of each of the two converging line sets.

iii. Effective Temperature Range (ETR) is a measure of the TIC's ability to see relatively small temperature differences in

cases when large temperature differences exist in the field of view [8]. In this test, the TIC is positioned such that it views a set of contrast bars having constant temperature while the temperature of a surface of equal size in the field of view is increased from near ambient to 550 °C. In general, as the hot surface temperature increases, the ability to display contrast of the bars decreases. The TIC is placed 1 m from the bar target, which is comprised of four vertical 1.27 cm diameter copper tubes placed 1.27 cm apart as depicted in Figure 2, resulting in a bar frequency of 0.04 cycles/mrad. A heated siloxane solution flows through the bars to maintain a temperature of 37 °C ± 1 °C (T_{bar}). The ambient temperature is 28 °C ± 1 °C ($T_{ambient}$). The bars and background are coated with black paint having an emissivity of 0.94 ± 0.05. An extended area blackbody having a 178 mm square surface is used as the radiation source. It is important that the emitting surface of the blackbody appear in the center of the image displayed by the thermal imager, while the heated bars appear at one side.

Figure 2: Effective temperature range thermal target. All temperatures are held constant except T_{hot} , which increases from ambient to 550 °C. The dashed lines indicate regions of interest for image processing.

C. Perception Test Design

The firefighter use case we address is one in which the firefighter is called to respond to a possible fire: a person has smelled fire and has reported this to the fire department. There is no visible fire. Consequently, the firefighter uses the TIC to locate and identify hot spots hidden behind walls, in furniture, under rugs, etc. This use case is our performance task and represents approximately 80 % of the responses of firefighters where TICs would be used. To determine the impact of image quality on a user’s ability to successfully perform meaningful tasks, a set of laboratory perception tests were conducted using firefighters of various ages, ranks, and levels of experience, all of whom use TICs on the job. The test subjects viewed thermal image scenes on computer monitors of a residential living room and an office. The subjects were instructed to identify any observed fire hazards by clicking on its perceived location or, if no hazard was perceived to be present in the image, by clicking on a “No Hazard” button. Each response was scored as either correct or incorrect based on the true location of the hazard within the image.

The primary IQIs C , B , R , and N of our high quality reference thermal test images were degraded in varying degrees such that the effect of each of these IQIs on the ability of a firefighter to perform a task could be quantified and modeled.

These IQIs were chosen based on their relevance to the operational performance requirements of the TICs. While there is not a 1-to-1 correspondence between each of these IQIs and the previously described laboratory tests, the imager’s performance regarding these IQIs can be deduced. For example, the imager’s ability to depict contrast is assessed in all the imager tests conducted. The relative temperature of surfaces in the field of view test provided an indication of brightness. Broadband noise and spatial resolution are directly related to the NU and R tests described in Section II B, respectively.

One hundred eighty (180) different reference images were produced with particular consideration given to a variety of robustness factors, e.g., placement of the potential fire hazard within the image, the size and shape of the potential fire hazard, and the amount of thermal clutter within the test image. The robustness factors were designed to capture influences on test subject performance that were not related to the IQIs. Each of the 180 reference images was degraded to 25 different IQI settings, resulting in 4500 different test images. The 25 IQI settings were developed by employing a statistical Taguchi parameter experiment design [9] to efficiently combine 5 levels of degradation for each of the primary IQIs C , B , R , and N .

III. MEASUREMENT ANALYSIS

Our goal is to develop a statistical model that relates the probability of successfully performing a perception task to the IQI values. The form and coefficients of this model are determined from the data obtained during the rigorous human perception tests.

Due to the known interdependence of the four IQIs it was immediately apparent that separate, individual models – mimicking the performance tests described earlier – would not adequately describe the perception task performance. To accommodate the interactions between IQIs and the fact that the results of the perceptions tests were binary (correct/incorrect), a multiple logistic regression model [10] containing all four IQIs, all second-order quadratic terms, and all two-term interactions is leveraged. The model is presented in its most compact form in the following equation:

$$P = \frac{e^{\beta'X}}{1 + e^{\beta'X}} \quad (2)$$

where P is the probability of successfully identifying the fire hazard, or absence of a fire hazard, in an image. The product $\beta'X$ represents:

$$\beta'X = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_1^2 + \dots + \beta_8 X_4^2 + \beta_9 X_1 X_2 + \dots + \beta_{14} X_3 X_4 \quad (3)$$

where the X_i represent the IQIs and the β_i are the coefficients determined through the regression modeling process.

Many forms of the regression model were considered with cross validation methods used to decide the final form of the model described by Equation (2). Using a randomly selected subset consisting of 2/3 of the perception test data, the

considered regression model forms using the four IQIs were fit and associated regression coefficients obtained defining a four-dimensional response surface. Based on the model fit, the probability of successfully completing the recognition task was predicted at each of the 25 IQI settings used in the perception tests. These predictions represent points on the four-dimensional surface. From the remaining 1/3 of the perception test data, an empirical estimate of the probability of the test subjects successfully completing the recognition task was calculated at each of the 25 IQI settings. The difference between the empirical estimate and the model predicted value was computed. Beginning with the random creation of the two datasets, this process was repeated 100 times with results of several of the considered model forms displayed in Figure 3. In the left panel, only the values of the four IQIs are included in the model, resulting in relatively large deviations from the raw data. The model underlying the middle panel includes the four IQIs and all two-way interactions resulting in a significant decrease in deviations as compared to the four IQIs alone. The right panel displays the deviations observed when considering the final model described in Equation (2).

Figure 3: Cross validation results for several considered model forms.

The adequacy of the fit of the ultimate model represented by Equation (2) was then assessed using the entire dataset by comparing the average of the test subjects’ responses for each of the 25 IQI settings to the model predicted values. The results displayed in Figure 4 show the high level of correlation between observed results (test subject responses) and the model predicted values.

A final check of the perception model was a simple “sanity check” to see if the model predictions fell within reasonably expected values. For this exercise, all but one of the four primary IQIs were held constant at their mid-range values while the remaining IQI was varied across its range. The resulting shape of the model predictions for each of the IQIs is shown in Figure 5. The results of the sanity check are generally as expected except for larger values of N , in which case the perception model predicts an improvement in the

ability of firefighters to identify a potential fire hazard. Upon further examination, it was found that these unexpected results occur in a range of N values (> 0.6) for which the model must be extrapolated. The range of values used to build the model did not extend far enough into the high range of N .

Figure 4: A comparison of the observed and model predicted values for the probability of successfully completing the perception task. The plot character represents the IQI setting (1-25). Perfect correlation falls at the 45° diagonal.

Figure 5: Sanity check plot showing the shape of model predictions for each of the IQIs as it is varied across its range while the other IQIs are held constant at their mid-range values.

To optimize the perception testing procedure and reduce test subject fatigue, the range of values used for the IQIs in the degraded images were chosen in an attempt to explore the $0.6 \leq P \leq 0.9$ region of the probability of successfully performing the fire hazard identification task. The reasoning was that collecting data from images in which none of the test subjects were able to identify anything did not yield valuable information for the purposes of this work. Likewise, using images in which all test subjects were able to identify the fire hazard would not provide useful information from which to construct the model. Therefore, no images were degraded to “zero” values of any of the primary IQIs. Future

improvements to the model will tighten up the predictions at both extremes; meanwhile, the model provides very good predictions throughout the range of IQI values upon which it was developed.

IV. APPLICATION

In the following three subsections, the perception model is used to predict the image quality performance of five fire service thermal imagers. The data used for the C, B, R, and N values in the model were collected using the laboratory test methods described in Section II. In some cases, the thermal imagers were not subjected to the full gamut of tests due to testing equipment failures.

i. Nonuniformity. Results from the *NU* test, in terms of the probability of success, P , are shown in Figure 6. An automatic mode shift is a method used in thermal imagers that employ microbolometer detectors to extend the dynamic range of the imager by decreasing the integration time that the thermal scene is exposed to the detector array. A side effect of operating at the shorter integration time is reduced thermal sensitivity. While this effect is not apparent in the *NU* results presented here, it is possible that for a given target temperature, the imager may automatically shift for one of the three tests conducted but not others if the mode shift algorithm is not triggered. The mode shift algorithm is a proprietary process and can depend on many conditions in the thermal scene, including, but not limited to, target temperature. This phenomenon can make testing the imagers problematic if the target temperature and other conditions are very close to the mode shift conditions.

Figure 6: Results of the nonuniformity (NU) test in terms of the probability of success, P . The uncertainty expressed in these test measurements is a combination of Type A (statistical) and Type B (other), with a coverage factor of 2 resulting in a 95 % confidence interval.

ii. Spatial Resolution. Results from the *R* test, in terms of the probability of success, P , are shown in Figure 7. While the probabilities of success for Imagers 1, 3, and 5 are relatively comparable, the probability of success for imager 2 is

significantly lower with a value below 30 %. Imager 4 displayed the most desirable results for the *R* test with a probability of success of 80 %.

Figure 7: Results of the spatial resolution (R) test in terms of the probability of success, P . The uncertainty expressed in these test measurements is a combination of Type A (statistical) and Type B (other), with a coverage factor of 2 resulting in a 95 % confidence interval.

iii. Effective Temperature Range. Results from the effective temperature range (*ETR*) test, in terms of the probability of success, P , for Imagers 3, 4, and 5 are shown in Figure 8. Technical difficulties with the blackbody used as the hot surface prevented the collection of data for Imagers 1 and 2. Three tests were conducted for each imager. Mode shifts can be observed as jumps in the data near the same hot surface temperature for all three tests. Imagers 3 and 4 produced higher P values after the mode shifts. Imager 5 did not display a pronounced mode shift.

V. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

There are different components of uncertainty in the measurements made with the equipment used in the tests discussed in this report. Type A uncertainties are those that are evaluated using statistical methods and Type B uncertainties are those that are estimated using other means, such as experience with a particular type of equipment. For this work, the Type A uncertainties are the standard deviations of the three test results per TIC per test method. The Type B uncertainties we used are derived from instrument specifications. Type B uncertainties are evaluated by estimating the upper and lower limits for the quantity in question such that the probability that the quantity would fall within the upper and lower limits is essentially 100 %. After estimating the uncertainties by Type A and Type B analysis, the results are combined in quadrature to yield the combined standard uncertainty. When the combined standard uncertainty is multiplied by a coverage factor of two, the result is the expanded uncertainty which corresponds to a 95 % confidence interval (2σ). This procedure is described in detail in [11]. The error bars shown in the figures reflect initial

uncertainty values. A more rigorous uncertainty analysis is being developed to include the propagation of the measurement uncertainties (Type A and Type B) as well as the statistical uncertainty in the regression model coefficients.

Figure 8: Results of the effective temperature range (*ETR*) in terms of the image quality indicator results, *P*, for Imagers 3, 4, and 5. Each colored line represents the results of one test.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated a method to objectively and scientifically characterize the technical performance of an imager for use in a given perception task. This method was demonstrated using passive long-wave infrared imagers

(thermal infrared cameras) used by the fire service. Specifically, a multi-variate human perception model that predicts the probability of firefighters to identify a potential fire hazard in an infrared image was developed and used to assess the image quality produced by fire service thermal imagers.

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